

The Homeric Hymn to Demeter

also known as “Homeric Hymn 2”

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Entry tags: Hymn, Religious Group, Ancient Mediterranean, Text, Classical Indo-European, Indo-European, Ancient Greek text, Language, Greek Cult, Greek Religions, Graeco-Phrygian, Greek

The Homeric Hymn to Demeter is one of 33 surviving ancient Greek hymns traditionally attributed to Homer (though modern scholars no longer believe that any of the Hymns were composed by the composer or composers of the Iliad and the Odyssey). The Homeric Hymn to Demeter (sequentially the second of the Homeric Hymns) is 495 lines long, making it one of the longest Homeric Hymns. The Hymn to Demeter uses a language and style that is particularly close to that found in the Homeric and Hesiodic epics, so it is usually argued that the Hymn was composed not long after these epics, perhaps between the late seventh century and the middle of the sixth century BCE. The Hymn describes the abduction of Demeter's daughter Penelope by Hades, the ruler of the underworld, and Demeter's subsequent attempt to retrieve her daughter. The Hymn also presents a mythical account for the origins of the Mysteries of Demeter and Kore at Eleusis.

Date Range: 600 BCE - 550 BCE

Region: Classical Greece

Region tags: Europe, Western Europe

Roughly the area encompassing the core of Classical Greek culture.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Richardson, N. J., *The Homeric Hymn to Demeter*, 2nd ed. (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1978)
- Source 2: Foley, Helene P., *The Homeric Hymn to Demeter: Translation, Commentary, and Interpretive Essays* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1994)
- Source 3: Clinton, Kevin, *Myth and Cult: The Iconography of the Eleusinian Mysteries* (Stockholm: Svenska Institutet i Athen, 1992)

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.efada.gr/en-us/Archaeological-Sites-Monuments/Eleusis/Archaeological-Site-of-Eleusis>

– Source 1 Description: Introduction to the archaeological site of Eleusis

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/text?doc=Perseus%3Atext%3A1999.01.0137%3Ahymn%3D2>

– Source 1 Description: Original text and translation of the Hymn

– Source 2 URL: <https://chs.harvard.edu/primary-source/homeric-hymn-to-demeter-sb/>

– Source 2 Description: Translation of the Hymn by Gregory Nagy

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Notes: The Homeric Hymns were performed and to some extent also transmitted orally. The Hymns, including the Hymn to Demeter, appear to have been composed within an oral framework and with oral poetic techniques (use of formulaic phraseology, traditional structures, etc.). But the Hymns were also composed at a time when literacy was becoming widespread in Greece, and would have been written down from an early date; exactly how long after composition the poems were written down is unknown, however.

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Papyrus

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– Yes

Notes: The language of the Homeric Hymn to Demeter is highly evocative of early oral Greek poetry, with many words and phrases found in Homer, Hesiod, and other early poets.

Reference: Richardson, N.. The Homeric Hymn to Demeter. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1978. p.30-56

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– No

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– No

Notes: The language of the Homeric Hymn to Demeter is largely the "traditional" Greek of Homer; there is some indication of Atticism in the language of this specific hymn, but to what

extent this is reflective of the origins and/or composition of the hymn or of the content of the hymn (i.e., the Attic cult of Demeter and Kore at Eleusis) is uncertain.

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– No

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Other [specify]: Not applicable

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– Yes

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– No

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Homeric Hymn to Demeter, like the other Homeric Hymns, was composed for oral performance. It is usually assumed that these would have been larger public performances associated with religious festivals, though contests and/or feasts at the houses of nobles would have also been a plausible venue for these poems. Consequently, it is impossible to determine the exact size of the audience typically present at performances of the Homeric Hymns.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Notes: The Homeric Hymns appear to have been typically performed as prooimia, or preludes to longer poetic (probably epic) performances. The context for these performances was probably connected with religious ritual (e.g., religious festivals), but the Hymns themselves were not part of the ritual per se. The Homeric Hymn to Demeter, as one of the longer Homeric Hymns, probably eventually became an independent performance; but we can only speculate as to where and when it was typically performed.

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: There is only one Medieval manuscript of the Homeric Hymn to Demeter (the Mosquensis manuscript, usually abbreviated "M"). There are, however, a number of papyrus and other fragments preserving parts of the text that supplement our knowledge of the text. Overviews and references to the manuscript and papyrus tradition and how it shapes our understanding of the text can be found in most modern editions of the Greek text (especially in the apparati critici).

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The Homeric Hymn to Demeter is one of the Homeric Hymns (traditionally given as the second Homeric Hymn).

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Prooimion (poetic prelude) to longer narrative poetic performance (especially epic)

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Vocabulary

Notes: The Hymn draws extensively on the vocabulary and phraseology of Greek epic, especially Homer

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text describes events surrounding the abduction of Demeter's daughter Persephone by Hades, the god of the afterlife.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– I don't know

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: Though Zeus is not the central character of the poem, all the events described in the Hymn are either directly or indirectly sanctioned by him.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– Yes

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– No

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: Not applicable

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Can reward

– Yes

↳ Can punish

– Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– Yes

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– Yes

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– Yes

↳ Can be hurt?

– Yes

Notes: There are myths that represent Zeus being hurt, such as some versions of the Typhon myth.

↳ Can be tricked?

– Yes

Notes: There are myths that represent Zeus being tricked, e.g., the myth of how Prometheus tricked Zeus into accepting the inedible parts of animals for sacrifices.

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– Yes

Notes: There are myths that represent Zeus being imprisoned, such as some versions of the Typhon myth.

- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
 - Specify: Not applicable

- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession
 - No
 - ↳ Through divination practices
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
 - ↳ Other form of communication with living
 - No

- ↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?
 - No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

Notes: The text describes the appearance of several supernatural beings, including Hades, Persephone, and Demeter.

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– No

Notes: Typically the gods of the Homeric Hymn to Demeter cannot see everywhere; the sun god Helios, however, can see everywhere in the day, and it is thus he who finally reveals to Demeter what had happened to her daughter.

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– No

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– No

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– No

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

Notes: In the text, Demeter punishes Metanira for interrupting her attempt to make her son immortal.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: Demeter initially communicates with human beings (the royal family of Eleusis) in disguise, but also communicates with them after revealing her true identity.

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

Notes: The gods were believed to communicate with human beings through dreams, though this is not illustrated in the text itself.

↳ In trance possession?

– No

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

Notes: Celeus, Metanira, and other human figures with whom Demeter communicates in the text are not religious specialists.

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: Not applicable

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

Notes: Demeter's grief at the loss of her daughter Persephone forms the central conflict of the text.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Yes

Notes: The text features the famous episode in which Hades tricks Persephone into eating some pomegranate seeds, as a result of which she can never leave the underworld for good.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

–Specify: Not applicable

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: Not applicable

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god visible to anyone in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Demeter appears to Celeus and Metanira, initially in disguise and later in her true form as a goddess.

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god hidden from anyone in the text?

– Yes

Notes: See notes on previous question.

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: Not applicable

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

Notes: Demeter punishes Celeus and Metanira in the text because Metanira interrupts her attempt to make her son Demophoon immortal.

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

Notes: See notes on previous question.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– Yes

Notes: Done out of anger

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– No

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– No

↳ Political failure?

– No

↳ Defeat in battle?

– No

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– No

Notes: Demeter causes extensive famine in the text, but this is presented as a result of her grief over losing Persephone rather than a punishment of any specific group.

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– No

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Sickness or illness?

– No

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– No

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– Yes

Notes: There is some indication that Demeter's punishment of Celeus and Metanira will involve misfortune for their descendants, including war.

↳ Other?

–Specify: Not applicable

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

Notes: Demeter's attempt to make Demophoon immortal can be interpreted as a reward for the hospitality shown to her by Demophoon's parents.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– Yes

Notes: The cult of Demeter and Kore at Eleusis taught that initiates received rewards in the afterlife, and these are mentioned briefly in the text.

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Consists of eternal happiness?

– Yes

↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?

– No

↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized?

– Yes

↳ Consists of good luck?

– No

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– No

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– No

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– No

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– Yes

Notes: As goddess of agriculture, the main rewards bestowed by Demeter in this life seem to consist of healthy crops and good weather.

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– Yes

Notes: It is said in the text that Demophoon grew up like an immortal after Demeter nursed him, even though Demeter did not succeed in making him fully immortal.

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: Not applicable

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Notes: Though some elements of the text can be interpreted eschatologically (e.g., Persephone's journey to the underworld) and eschatological teachings were part of the cult of Demeter and Kore at Eleusis (whose mythical origins are described in the text), the text itself does not contain a true eschatology.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

Notes: In the text, Demeter requires the people of Eleusis to build a sanctuary for her and prescribes certain rituals for her worship.

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The major festivals at Eleusis involved tens of thousands of participants.

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– Yes

Notes: There is evidence of wine and other intoxicants being used in connection with the cult of Demeter and Kore at Eleusis.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

↳ Drama?

– No

↳ Comedy?

– Yes

Notes: There are comic elements in the text, most famously the scene in which Iambe cheers up Demeter.

↳ Tragedy?

– No

↳ Epic entertainment?

– No

Notes: The Homeric Hymn to Demeter, like the other Homeric Hymn, likely originated as a proimion or prelude to an epic performance, but the hymn itself is not an epic.

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Notes: In the text, Demeter explains that she will prescribe her rituals to the people of Eleusis, but the text itself does not specify these prescriptions.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A city-state

Notes: The Greek world was split up into numerous city-states (or poleis) at the time that the Homeric Hymns were composed. It is unknown in which city-state the Homeric Hymn to Demeter originated, though its contents connect it closely to the city-state of Eleusis in the region of Attica.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Not applicable.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Not applicable

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Homeric Hymns seem to have been taught and to have been a subject of scholarly study in antiquity. They are still taught at universities today.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: The text makes briefly and allusively mentions that the people of Eleusis will war with one another.

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

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